

CHANGES OF SOME PROPERTIES OF THE SOIL AND PLANTS COVERING AROUND THE AREA OF METALLURGICAL INDUSTRY

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Abstract. Metallurgical waste is considered to be an industrial sector that has a negative impact on a large scale. for this purpose, the analysis of the observations and research results carried out in our Republic and on the world scale is presented on this topic

Key words: metallurgy, heavy metals, industrial waste, lead (Pb), zinc (Zn), remediation, chlorosis

Comprehensive reforms are being carried out in all spheres of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including legal, scientific and practical work in the agricultural sphere. Article 55 of the Constitution of our country stipulates that "Land, underground resources, water, flora and fauna and other natural resources are national wealth, they must be used wisely and are under state protection." Also, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopts Decisions on relevant State Programs. these legal documents set urgent tasks for relevant organizations, enterprises and scientists in this field to protect soil from pollution, restore, maintain and increase its productivity.

Sources of environmental pollution with chemical elements and substances are mainly metal production industrial waste, combustion products of various fuels, car smoke and exhaust gases, chemical preparations used in agriculture, etc. Mercury, lead, cadmium, arsenic, selenium, and fluorine elements are among the most dangerous chemical elements for the environment and, of course, for humans, among them mercury, lead, and cadmium are the most dangerous.

According to the data, 150 thousand tons of copper, 120 thousand tons of zinc, 90 thousand tons of lead, 12 thousand tons of nickel, 1.5 tons of molybdenum, 800 tons of cobalt fall into the soil by the metallurgical industry in the world. [2].

Pollution caused by metallurgical activities are:

- ferrous metallurgy releases mineral compounds, coal, ash, cyanides, phenol compounds, acidic solutions;
- during extraction of Cu, Zn, Al in non-ferrous metallurgy, cyanides, acids, heavy metals, chlorine.

The main types of pollution in the metal processing plant: excavation, mining, gravel extraction, open pits, pollution through waste released to the soil,

abandoned basins, pollution with wastewater, inorganic compounds, metals, salts and acids. production forces produce 80% iron oxides by casting steel[3]. Heavy metals deposited on the soil cover affect the biological, biochemical, agrochemical, chemical properties of the soil, as well as the air, food and water regime. in foreign countries and in our republic, a number of scientists have conducted research on the properties of soil contaminated with heavy metals and methods of cleaning. heavy metals have a strong effect on soil organic matter transformation, soil microorganisms, enzyme activity, soil respiration activity, nitrogen assimilation [5]

The results of scientific research show that 60% of dry and irrigated soils are subject to varying degrees of salinity, erosion, and are contaminated with pesticides and heavy metals. In the cities of Tashkent, Chirchik, Yangiyol, Chinoz, Angren, Almalik, Ohangaron, metallurgical and chemical industries and densely populated areas, the oasis soils are polluted by industrial, construction and household wastes to varying degrees [12].

The scale of impacts on the environment (taking into account the soil layer) as a result of the production activities of mining and metallurgical enterprises is manifested mainly in three directions: 1) erosion of the landscape (soil, vegetation , fauna relief). 2) intactoccupation of lands adjacent to landscapes with production waste; 3) distribution of production materials and waste along transportation routes. In the settlements located near the waste warehouses of the copper beneficiation factory and the lead beneficiation factory of the Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Combine, dust was raised in unsuitable climatic conditions (by wind) [9].

The mechanism of influence of heavy metals on the agrochemical properties of the soil is such that a certain type of heavy metal that enters the soil affects the activity and biological activity of soil microorganisms. as a result, the death of microorganisms and weakening of soil biological activity are observed. The high amount of heavy metals in soils adapted to irrigated agriculture for a long time is explained by the amount of gypsum in the soil, salinity, erosion and sulfate deficiency. This causes metals to accumulate in large quantities in plants[11].

Emissions from the metallurgical industry account for approximately 15% of the total amount of emissions from all stationary (stagnant) sources into the atmosphere. Despite the nature protection measures, "OTMK" OJSC remains a major source of atmospheric air pollution in the Republic. 12% of waste and 26% of sulfur dioxide emitted by all stationary (stagnant) sources in the republic are accounted for by this organization. in some years, in the city of

Almalyk, atmospheric air pollution with sulfur dioxide exceeded the sanitary-hygienic standards by 5 times [14].

Sh.T.Kholikulov stated that as a result of the long-term operation of the Samarkand Chemical Combine, various solid wastes are emitted into the environment and various smoke exhaust gases are emitted from the chimneys of the combine, at different levels in the wind direction contaminated the soil with heavy metals application of organic and mineral fertilizers to the soil in cotton fields has a positive effect on reducing the amount of mobile heavy metals in the arable (0-30 cm) layer of the soil. among studied plants, corn takes the first place in absorbing heavy metals. Among cultivated plants, cotton is the most important in absorbing heavy metals [13]. Atmospheric pollution causes serious damage to all plants, including agricultural crops, green areas of the city and its surroundings. Toxic substances have a negative effect on the direct surface of plants, as well as on the roots through the soil [15].

Heavy metal pollution is a serious threat in many countries of the world, including China. The soil of 10.18% of farms and 13.86% of grain production lands has deteriorated due to the influence of heavy metals. Henan, Shandong and Sichuan intensive industrial areas are more polluted than others [7].

Lead (Pb) is an example of a potential heavy metal, it is not an essential element and does not play any role in the process of cellular metabolism, but is easily absorbed and accumulates in various parts. Lead accumulation in soil inhibits seed germination and slows seedling growth, reducing germination percentage, germination index, root-shoot length, tolerance index, and root and shoot dry mass[8]. In general, Zn is not considered a highly phytotoxic metal, but the Zn content found in surrounding contaminated soils often exceeds the amount required as a nutrient and can cause phytotoxicity. Of Zn toxicity in various plants also causes chlorosis in young leaves, and after prolonged exposure, chlorosis spreads to older leaves as well[6].

The use of microbes as an alternative technology to improve plant metal tolerance has gained momentum recently. Plant-associated microbes reduce metal accumulation in plant tissues and also help reduce the bioavailability of metals in soil through various mechanisms[11]. Greenhouse experiment to study the efficacy of heavy metal resistant plant growth promoting bacterial strains (HMT-PGPB) (Alcaligenes faecalis MG257493.1, Bacillus cereus MG257494.1 and Alcaligenes faecalis MG966440 against all heavy metals) conducted..the results showed that the application of these HTM-PGPB strains as

sorghum biofertilizers can help reduce the toxic effects of heavy metals on the plant and increase the growth characteristics[4].

From the given data it can be concluded that the presence of sources that cause the risk of pollution and the living of the population around them, as well as the decrease in the productivity of polluted soils, in some cases leaving the state of agricultural use and the change in the bioecology of plant cover requires finding a solution to this problem as an urgent issue today.

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